

RESEARCH OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF S SHARQ-UNIVERSAL-SMK LLC

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Abstract. *This article discusses the development of a new product, research in the field of innovative marketing, various methods for updating the product range, and various types and levels of market novelty of the products offered.*

Keywords: *enterprises, product range, market, research, consumer, competition, equipment.*

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ МАРКЕТИНГОВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ООО «С ШАРК-УНИВЕРСАЛ-СМК»

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются разработка нового товара, исследования в области инновационного маркетинга, различные методы обновления товарного ассортимента, различные виды и уровни рыночной новизны предлагаемых товаров.*

Ключевые слова: *предприятия, ассортимент, рынок, исследование, потребитель, конкуренция, оборудование.*

INTRODUCTION

In a market economy, updating the range of products is becoming one of the important areas of marketing activities of enterprises. This is due primarily to high competition in the consumer market, and secondly, to the dynamics of changes in market conditions. The tastes and preferences of consumers under the influence of market supply are changing rapidly. Based on this, in our final qualifying work, the task of organizing the introduction of new products to the market is considered. As a result of the research, we have come to the following conclusions.

In modern marketing theory, the development of a new product becomes one of the key elements of the competitiveness of enterprises. Research is actively conducted in the field of innovative marketing, which allows enterprises to use various methods for updating the product range.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A new product is the results of industrial research of an enterprise that have a market novelty. There are various types and levels of market novelty of the products offered.

Each product has its own life cycle in the market. At the end of its life cycle, it must be upgraded or withdrawn from the market. In accordance with this, enterprises are constantly developing and introducing new products. The development of a new product goes through several stages from market research to marketing support for promoting goods to various segments. An important component of introducing new products to the market is the formation of a pricing strategy for new products.

The pasta market is rapidly changing and competitive. In Samarkand, there are a large number of small enterprises for the production of pasta. Therefore, S Sharq-Universal-SMK LLC needs to constantly increase its product range. The equipment of the enterprise allows the production of new products with low costs for modernization.

At the same time, in order to master the release of new products, it is necessary to carry out a number of marketing activities, such as researching the properties of a new product, market research, organizing production and packaging, pricing and methods of promoting goods.

The enterprise is located in a spacious and comfortable building, meets sanitary and hygienic requirements.

The main criterion for selecting premises for the production of pasta is the most suitable size (area). It should contain the main area for the production line and other equipment, a warehouse and an office for administration and management dealing with management and marketing issues.

The main workshop should have a high ceiling (at least 3 meters), opportunities for comfortable yet compact placement of machines and equipment, features that ensure absolute safety for both employees and end products. The area allocated for the warehouse should be equipped with special racks for storing raw materials and auxiliary equipment, components for the hardware.

The existence of this room implies the presence of ventilation equipment, controllers and microclimate regulators in it. It is not recommended to allocate a plot with an area of more than 100 square meters for a warehouse in a small enterprise for the production of pasta. The office space should be small in size with average ceiling height and windows. Presumably, it should be located on the ground floor (for ease of contact with buyers, intermediaries and suppliers), but this is not necessary.

RESULTS

To start a small business, it is recommended to select appropriately qualified personnel with at least 3-4 years of experience in the production and sale of food products, since the acquisition of work skills by employees can create too great economic risks for activities, even if the business is properly organized as a whole. When applying for a job, it is important not only to study diplomas, entries in the work book and recommendations, but also to personally talk with a person, inviting him to solve several non-standard situational problems. This technique is good not only for office workers (marketers, managers), but also for production personnel: there are more difficulties in work and dangers. You can immediately determine who in an extreme situation will not be confused and will show quick wit and initiative. Often, in food production plants, women between the ages of 26 and 55 tend to oversee the production line. The work associated with bringing raw materials to the equipment and loading it is done by men aged 27 to 60 years. To work with the external environment of the company in the face of customers, intermediaries and suppliers, young people under 33 are best suited, since, according to statistics, they are more open to innovations and market trends, more sociable and non-standard in making managerial and marketing decisions. Any small business has a functional organizational structure in which all managerial, administrative and control powers are concentrated in the hands of the head. In the charter and internal documents of the company, it is necessary to describe in detail and unambiguously the areas of work of each employee, occupying a particular workplace, staffing and the nature of the relationship between employees. Initially, it is necessary to maintain a corporate culture and a pleasant working atmosphere in even the smallest team.

S Sharq-Universal-SMK LLC employs 46 people in total, of which 29 people work in production and 17 people in wholesale trade.

All employees of the production workshop are skilled and trained for the production of pasta.

Table 1

Information about the employees of S Sharq-Universal-SMK LLC as of March 2022

No.	Job title	Wage	Amount of workers	General salary
one	Shop manager	680000	one	680000
2	Accountant	530000	one	530000
3	Warehouse Manager	680000	one	680000
four	laboratory assistant	400000	one	400000
5	Technologist	400000	3	1200000
6	Presser	400000	3	1200000
7	Flour sifting and serving worker	280000	6	1680000
eight	Packer	280000	6	1680000
9	An electrician	280000	one	280000
ten	Security guard	150000	2	300000
eleven	Cook	280000	one	280000
12	Cleaner	150000	one	150000
	Total		27	9060000

This table shows that the monthly wage fund at the enterprise is 9,060,000 soums, and the average wage is 335,556 soums.

DISCUSSION

Based on the above data, it is possible to illustrate the organizational structure of S Sharq-Universal-SMK LLC.

The organizational structure of an enterprise is understood as the composition, subordination, interaction and distribution of work among departments and management bodies, between which certain relations are established regarding the implementation of authority, flow of commands and information.

There are several types of organizational structures: linear, functional, linear-functional, divisional, adaptive. Let us consider the main characteristics of these structures.

The linear structure is characterized by the fact that each department is headed by a leader who has concentrated all management functions in his hands and exercises sole leadership of his subordinate employees. Its decisions, passed along the chain "from top to bottom", are obligatory for implementation by lower links. He, in turn, is subordinate to a higher manager.

On this basis, a hierarchy of managers of this management system is created (for example, a site foreman, a shop manager, an enterprise director), i.e. the principle of unity of command is implemented, which assumes that subordinates carry out the orders of one leader. A higher management body does not have the right to give orders to any performers, bypassing their immediate superior.

The linear management structure is used, as a rule, by small and medium-sized enterprises that carry out simple production, in the absence of broad cooperative ties between enterprises.

The functional structure involves the specialization of the performance of individual management functions. Separate subdivisions (or functional performers) are allocated for their implementation. The functional organization of management is based on the horizontal division of managerial labor. Instructions of the functional body within its competence are obligatory for production units.

The functional management structure is usually used in large enterprises. In the US, for example, this structure is used by 25% of large firms.

The linear-functional structure makes it possible to largely eliminate the shortcomings of both linear and functional management. With this structure, the purpose of functional services is to prepare data for line managers in order to make competent decisions or emerging production and management tasks. The role of functional bodies (services) depends on the scale of economic activity and the structure of enterprise management as a whole. The larger the company and the more complex its management system, the more branched out the apparatus it has. In this regard, the issue of coordination of the activities of functional services is acute.

Linear-functional management structures are used in most enterprises. The divisional (or departmental) management structure is the most common form of management organization of a modern industrial firm. Its meaning is that independent divisions are almost completely responsible for the development, production and marketing of homogeneous products (divisional-product management structure) or independent departments are fully responsible for economic results in certain regional markets (divisional-regional management structure).

Rice. 1. Organizational structure of S Sharq-Universal-SMK LLC.

Analysis of the production process at S Sharq-Universal-SMK LLC. The production process is a complex of operations for the extraction and processing of raw materials and materials and their transformation into finished products. Depending on the purpose of the manufactured products, the production activity of the enterprise is divided into the following types: main, auxiliary and service industries and facilities.

For a complete understanding of these stages, we will characterize each of them and give examples from international practice.

Flour preparation. Flour preparation consists of: weighing, mixing, sifting, magnetic cleaning. Mixing different batches of flour of the same variety in a certain ratio is carried out to improve any indicator due to the best raw materials. The use of improvers requires thorough mixing of batches of flour in special flour mixers.

Mixing is also necessary for the container storage of small batches of raw materials, especially if the necessary microclimate for storage is not maintained in the warehouses.

Depending on where and for how long each bag is located, the moisture content of the flour in it can change quite strongly over time. The difference in humidity, in bags, can reach 1÷2%, which can lead to unstable operation of the pasta press and the entire line as a whole.

Sifting is carried out to separate foreign particles that accidentally get into the flour, such as: villi, threads, paper, dried lumps of flour. For sifting, usually used are burats, centrifugal sieves, sieves, and other equipment equipped with metal sieves with openings ranging in size from 1.0 to 1.6 mm.

Magnetic cleaning of flour is carried out with permanent magnets to remove metal impurities that could get into flour as a result of the operation of mechanisms. In the field of magnets, flour should move in a layer of 6-8 mm at a speed of no more than 0.5 m / s. Such a magnetic cleaning system is mandatory for pasta equipment. Every 4 hours of operation, the magnets are cleaned. Consider the next section is pasta production technologies.

Cooking pasta dough. Pasta dough, in its composition, is the simplest of all types of dough used in the production of flour products. Often, the recipe consists only of flour and water. The introduction of any additives and improvers significantly increases the cost of pasta and makes pasta production unprofitable. When kneading pasta dough, much less water is added to flour than for making other types of dough, such as bread dough. The finished pasta dough has a crumbly structure and only in the process of further pressing does it turn into a homogeneous mass suitable for shaping.

The mixing of ingredients, or kneading, takes place in continuous mixers that are part of the presses. Flour and water enter the dough mixer through dispensers, which are adjusted to certain doses before work, according to the recipe. There are single-trough mixers and multi-tub mixers, depending on the technology used.

When kneading dough from grains, a longer kneading time is required than from powdered flour, because the penetration of moisture into larger fractions takes a longer time. Therefore, the kneading should last about 20 minutes. This requires a multi-bunker mixing system. For kneading powdered flour, one hopper is enough, with a kneading time of about 10 minutes. Flour and water are fed into the flour mixer using continuous dispensers. According to the principle of action, dispensers can be volumetric and weight. In foreign equipment, a rotary volumetric dosing or screw dosing is usually used.

Compaction and molding of dough. In modern pasta factories, dough compaction and product molding takes place on screw pasta presses. They differ in the number of troughs (one-, two-, three-, and four-trough), in the number of pressing devices and in the shape of the matrix (round and rectangular).

Flour and water continuously flow into the inlet of the dough mixer and are picked up by the blades of the kneaders. Altering, the dough gradually moves to the opposite end of the

trough, where the crumbly dough is already ready. Through the through hole it enters the auger of the pressing device. When it rotates, the dough moves to the press head. The dough is compacted, turns into a dense dough mass, and forming in the matrix, it comes out of it in the form of pasta. When pressing and forming a viscous, dense dough, the temperature of the dough rises. To prevent overheating of the dough, cold water is supplied to the jacket of the pressing device. Also, the jacket of the press device is designed to warm up the cylinder before starting the press.

Pressing process. There are two types of pasta dough that differ in appearance and physical properties: free-flowing crumbly mass after kneading and compacted dough after pressing. Kneading - obtaining a crumbly, finely lumpy, free-flowing mass, evenly moistened throughout the volume. All flour particles must be completely saturated with moisture, so that with further refinement of the dough, in the screw chamber, their complete plasticization occurs.

The duration of the kneading is determined by two factors: the achievement of uniform moistening of the dough throughout the mass and the penetration of moisture into the flour particles. The more atomized the water is supplied to the kneading, the faster the kneading will take place.

For the production of pasta from bread flour, one trough is enough with a kneading time of 8÷10 minutes. In terms of volume and footprint, these presses are quite compact and suitable for production in small spaces. The intensity of kneading depends on the speed of rotation of the kneading shaft. The optimal rotation speed is about 100 rpm for a single kneading shaft.

Vacuum test. Vacuumization of the dough began to be used for the first time with the introduction of screw pasta presses, on which the pressing pressure did not exceed 60 kgf / cm², and this was not enough to obtain dense and durable pasta.

When molding the dough, which has undergone vacuum treatment, that is, air bubbles have been removed, the strength of raw products has increased by an average of 40% and the strength of dry products by an average of 20%.

In the presses of the first designs, evacuation was carried out in a screw chamber. The effectiveness of this method is low, due to the transience of the passage of the test vacuum channel and the difficulty of suction of air from the compacted dough mass.

Cutting raw pasta. The cutting of raw pasta is carried out immediately after pressing out. The goal is to prepare products for drying. Cutting consists in blowing, cutting and laying out pasta. The performance of the drying press, the consumption of raw materials and the quality of finished products depend on the quality of these operations. Blowing of products is carried out to prevent sticking of pasta, for better cutting. Products are usually blown with the air of the molding department - temperature ~ 25°C and humidity 60-70%. Molded and dried pasta is cut to the desired length by a cutting mechanism and laid out for drying on the drying surfaces of conveyor dryers, or on tray cassettes.

Drying, stabilization and cooling of pasta. To prevent the occurrence of biochemical processes, products are subjected to conservation by dehydration - drying to a moisture content of not more than 13%. Drying is the longest stage in the production of pasta. The quality indicators of the finished product, such as strength, vitreousness, acidity, structural integrity and appearance, depend on the correctness of this process. Very intensive drying leads to cracking, too long - to souring, drying in a layer - to the formation of ingots and deformation.

Drying is usually completed when the moisture content of the product reaches 13.5 ... 14%, so that after cooling, the moisture content is no more than 13%. Drying of short-cut pasta in conveyor dryers using traditional low-temperature modes is carried out in several stages:

1. pre-drying;
2. final drying;
3. cooling down;
4. stabilization.

Линия производства макарон

Rice. 3. Pasta production line.

The dryer itself is a thermally insulated and sealed tunnel, inside which belt conveyors are located one above the other. Raw products, evenly spaced by the stacker across the entire width of the working belt of the upper conveyor of the dryer, are sent to the opposite end of the dryer, where they are poured onto the second conveyor belt, etc. until the dried product comes out of the last tape. After leaving the dryer and after intensive blowing, the products are fed by the conveyor to the stabilization hopper, from where, after 4-5 hours of stabilization, the products are packed into containers by the packer.

Conveyor belts of conveyors are made of polyamide or metal mesh mesh, subjected to special heat treatment, which eliminates thermal stretching.

Pre-drying of products takes place on the upper tapes, isolated from external influences separately. On the upper belt, products are heated up to 50-55°C and moisture is actively removed by drying air of 60-65% humidity. The humidity of the product is reduced from 30-31% to 20-22%. Further, the drying capacity of the air is reduced to more gently remove moisture from the surface. Products are tempered. During this time, there is a loss of 2 - 3% of moisture and the moisture leveling of all layers of pasta dough. Temperature 45-50°C, humidity - about 80%.

The final drying takes place on the lower belts, which are blown with air $t=40-45^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $W=70-75\%$. The loss of moisture at this stage is still a few percent and the products at the output have 13-15% moisture. On the last tape, the products slowly cool down to 30 °C with a loss of 1-2% moisture.

CONCLUSIONS

In each zone, the monitoring and control system supports the necessary modes. Fans are controlled by sensors to ensure the correct air exchange inside the dryer and the necessary release of moist air outside the dryer. All data is displayed on an electronic display or a computer with a picture of a dryer - the whole picture of the drying process is before your eyes. It is easy to manage the process, knowing the recommended modes of the drying process. So, at the exit from the dryer, pasta has a moisture content of 11-12%. To relieve internal stresses in products,

it is desirable to subject them to treatment with superheated steam for 5-6 seconds. Humidification of the surface layer by 1-1.5% contributes to a more correct stabilization process. Cooling and stabilization should take place in an environment of equilibrium humidity, but maintaining the necessary microclimate is largely problematic, and in this case, moistening the surface layer with steam makes it possible to have drier air in the stabilization room without fear of cracking. The moisture gradient does not increase. The stabilization hopper must have internal partitions to separate products by type. Total cooling and stabilization time - 3-4 hours

Storage of finished pasta. To preserve the quality of pasta throughout the entire period from production to sale to consumers, it is recommended to store products at $t=30^{\circ}\text{C}$ no higher, in an environment of equilibrium humidity for a given moisture content of the product. Products should be stored in cardboard boxes or paper bags, with product moisture not exceeding 13%. Products intended for packaging in small cellophane containers up to 1 kg must have a moisture content of not more than 12%.

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